

Metal Chelate Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-5-Methyl-Benzophenone (*p*) Tolil

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2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (*p*) tolil (HMBT) is found to be a chelating agent for Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions. It gave a reddish brown bis-chelate (*pH* 10.0-10.8) with Cu^{2+} , a red bis-chelate (*pH* 9.0-9.8) with Ni^{2+} and a green bis-chelate (*pH* 10.8-11.5) with Co^{2+} . The composition of these chelates have been described on the basis of their elemental analysis. The complexes of Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} were paramagnetic and the nickel complex was diamagnetic. Copper can be estimated gravimetrically.

THE reagent having $-\text{O}-\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ system have been investigated by several workers.^{1,5} Schiff's bases of salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehydes were prepared and their copper chelates were studied by Calvin and Wilson.⁶ The use of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenoneanil as analytical reagent for Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} has been reported⁷. Schiff's bases obtained by condensing 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone with aniline, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline and *p*-anisidine have been employed as analytical reagent for Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} . 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (*o*)-tolil and 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone (*m*)-tolil have been studied as analytical reagent.¹² The present work deals with the preparation of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (*p*)-tolil by the method suggested by Reddelien⁹ and its chelates with copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II). This reagent gives reddish brown precipitate with Cu^{2+} at *pH* 10.0 to 10.8 and red precipitate with Ni^{2+} at *pH* 9.0 to 9.8 and green precipitate with Co^{2+} at *pH* 10.8 to 11.5. The copper can be estimated gravimetrically from solution containing Cu^{2+} ions alone or in presence of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} . The Ni (II) and Co (II) complexes do not get precipitated alongwith Cu (II) as it is found that they are formed only after refluxing the mixture of metal ions and ligand at the mentioned *pH* for 1 hr. and more. The addition of the reagent solution in warm metal ion solution precipitate only Cu (II) complex. The compositions of these complexes

have been discussed on the basis of their elemental analysis. The copper and cobalt complexes were found to be paramagnetic whereas the nickel complex was diamagnetic. The quantitative estimation of copper was done (Table 1).

Experimental

Preparation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (*p*) tolil :

2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone was prepared by Fries reaction of *p*-cresylbenzoate.¹⁰ 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (0.1 M), *p*-toluidine (0.1 M) and anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) were heated at 160° for ½ hr and then the temperature was raised to 180° for five min. It was cooled and the anil was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform was distilled out from the extract and the product was isolated.

It was crystallised from ethanol. Yellow crystals m.p. 100°. Yield 75%.

Found : C = 83.68%, H = 6.29%, N = 4.62%
Calculated for

($\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}$) C = 83.73%, H = 6.31%, N = 4.65%

Preparation of metal complex : One percent ethanolic solution of the reagent was used.

Copper complex : Cupric chloride solution (0.1M, 10 ml) was diluted to 100 ml and warmed upto 50°-60°. Excess of ammoniumhydroxide was added till blue coloured solution is formed. A calculated volume of reagent solution was added with stirring followed with the addition of little excess of the reagent to ensure complete precipitation. The complex was digested on water bath for 10 min and filtered. It was washed with water till free from chloride ions, then with ten percent ethanol and dried at 100°-110°. The chelate can be easily crystallised from benzene. The result of the estimation of copper from cupric chloride solution alone and in presence of Ni (II) and Co (II) are recorded in the Table

Found : Cu = 9.54, N = 4.20%

TABLE I. ESTIMATION OF Cu^{2+} IN THE SOLUTION OF Cu^{2+} ION ALONE AND IN PRESENCE OF Ni^{2+} OR Co^{2+} AT *pH* 10.8

Sr. No.	Wt. of the metal ion in mg	Wt. of complex in mg	Metal ion found in complex	Error in mg
1.	Cu^{2+} 62.5	650.0	62.3	-0.2
2.	Cu^{2+} 62.5 Ni^{2+} 58.5	650.4	62.3	-0.2
3.	Cu^{2+} 62.5 Co^{2+} 58.4	649.8	62.2	-0.3

Calculated for

$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO})_2$: Cu = 9.57, N = 4.22%

Nickel complex: Nickel complex was prepared by refluxing (1 hr) a requisite amount of reagent solution and nickel chloride solution (0.1M) with ammonium hydroxide and ammonium acetate at pH 9.0-9.5, in alcoholic medium, when a red coloured complex was obtained. It was filtered out, washed with water till free from chloride ions and then with little ethanol and dried at 100°-110°. It can be crystallised easily from benzene.

Found: Ni = 8.88, N = 4.22%

Calculated for

$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO})_2$: Ni = 8.91, N = 4.25%

Cobalt complex: It was prepared by refluxing (1 hr) a requisite amount of reagent solution with Co (II) chloride solution containing excess of ammonium hydroxide (pH 10.5-11.0) in alcoholic medium.

A green coloured complex was obtained which was filtered, washed with water till free from chloride ions and dried at 100°-110°. It can be crystallised from benzene.

Found: Co = 8.92, N = 4.20%

Calculated for

$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO})_2$: Co = 8.94, N = 4.25%

The quantitative estimation of nickel and cobalt was not possible.

All these metallic complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in alcohol, chloroform, benzene and other organic solvents.

The molecular weight determined by cryoscopic method was in agreement with the empirical formula weight, showing that these chelates were monomers, represented by the general formula $\text{M}(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO})_2$ where M = Cu, Ni and Co.

The magnetic moments of the chelates were obtained by Guoy balance method. It was found that magnetic moment of copper complex was $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.78$ BM, and for cobalt complex $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.64$ BM at 36° whereas the nickel complex was diamagnetic.

The absorption spectra of the chelates (in ethanol) in U.V. and visible region were recorded using unicam spectrophotometer, and Hilger H-700, 304 54542 Spectrophotometer.

Discussion

As the copper chelate (whether square planar or tetrahedral) has one unpaired electron, the calculated magnetic moment value, corresponding to the spin moment only is $\mu_s = 1.73$ BM. The observed value is $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.78$ BM is very close to μ_s value shows that there is no intrinsic orbital contribution. The unpaired electron of the d^9 configuration is in the b_{1g} orbital giving a ${}^2B_{1g}$ ground term. The μ_{eff} may be expected to be some 15% above the spin value.¹¹ The observed value is $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.78$ BM conforming

approximately to the predictions of the theory. The exact structure whether the chelate is square planar or tetrahedral can not be judged by magnetic moment value only.

The absorption spectra of copper chelate in ethanol shows a broad band around 370 nm and others at 260 nm and 227 nm. The expected absorption maxima in the visible range is not obtained. These absorption maxima obtained above are of the ligand part only as the ligand spectra shows the similar bands. The diffusion reflectance spectra of the copper chelate shows a very broad band between 500-450 nm.

Since Cu^{2+} is a one positron case it predicts that the following transitions of the positron

$$d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}; d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}; d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow (d_{zx}, d_{yz})$$

will give absorption bands lying very close together. In the present case the $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow (d_{zx}, d_{yz})$ band is shifted to the U.V. region and one band obtained between 500-450 nm in reflectance spectra consists only of the $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$, $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$.

The diamagnetic nature of nickel chelate suggest dsp^2 hybridization and square planar structure of the chelate. It shows absorption band at 418-420 nm, 336-227 nm and 257 nm.

The cobalt chelate is paramagnetic with $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.64$ BM. The absorption spectra shows that the absorption maxima are quite damped and broad. They are at 370 nm and 249 nm and a long tail of charge transfer band into visible region. From the magnetic properties, it can be assigned square planar configuration.

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